

Highly effective technology for ammonia abatement from industry operations[☆]

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ABSTRACT

The following paper presents a novel two-stage photochemical technology for efficient ammonia removal from industrial waste air. The study addresses especially ammonia captured during SCR and SNCR process in power plants. Technology combining photolytic reactor and wet scrubber is designed to effectively reduce ammonia emissions while recovering valuable nitrogen compounds in the form of liquid fertilizers. The photolytic reactor ammonia conversion rate reached up to 23 % depending on the air flow rate and ammonia initial concentration. Wet scrubber effectively absorbed approximately 98 % of ammonia into hydrogen peroxide solution. Second part of the study focuses on removal of absorbed ammonia from solution. Based on the experimental results pH in the range of 9,2–10,8 is required for ammonia to be oxidized to nitrites and nitrates. It was confirmed the current technology is capable of oxidizing over 45 % of absorbed ammonia. Even though, this technology offers a viable solution for industrial facilities to meet emission regulation while aligning with circular economy principles through nitrogen compounds recovery, further study is required and will be focused on improving oxidation rate of absorbed ammonia to nitrites and nitrates and utilization of solution as nitrogen fertilizer in agriculture.

1. Introduction

Ammonia emissions pose a significant environmental challenge, affecting air quality, human health and ecosystem balance [1]. Ammonia released from agriculture and industrial activities contributes to soil and water acidification, eutrophication of aquatic ecosystems, and the formation of harmful secondary particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) in the atmosphere [2,3]. Moreover, human exposure to ammonia can lead to severe health issues, including acute toxicity and corrosion of the skin and eyes [4].

While agriculture remains the primary source of ammonia pollution (81–94 %) [5], other significant ammonia contributors include industrial production, energy generation, waste incineration, and transportation. Globally, combustion processes, primarily the burning of fossil fuels and biomass, account for 12.2 ± 5.6 million tons (7–19 %) of ammonia emission annually [6–8]. In the Czech Republic, this amounts to 500–600 tons of ammonia per year [9].

The power, transport, and waste incineration industries historically struggled with high nitrogen oxides emissions. The introduction of

selective non-catalytic reduction technology (SNCR) in the 1970s partially addressed this issue, with subsequent developments in selective catalytic reduction (SCR) technologies [10]. However, these technologies, which use urea or ammonia water as reducing agents, can inadvertently lead to ammonia release into the environment, posing new challenges [11–13]. With SNCR/SCR technology being increasingly adopted by power plants and other facilities across the Czech Republic and other EU countries [14], there is a growing demand for ammonia removal technologies.

Several technologies have been developed to mitigate ammonia emissions, including biological filters, wet scrubbers, and catalytic or photocatalytic oxidation systems. Biofiltration and biological scrubbers are commonly used in agricultural applications due to their cost-effectiveness, although they often require large surface areas and are sensitive to operational conditions such as temperature and moisture [15,16]. Conventional wet scrubbers offer high removal efficiency for ammonia but typically require large volumes of acid or oxidizing agents, which increase operational costs and produce secondary waste streams [15]. Advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), especially those based on

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UV/H₂O₂ or TiO₂ photocatalysis, have shown promise for degrading ammonia in air or water under controlled conditions [17–19], but are rarely applied in systems designed for industrial exhausts with complex gas compositions.

Further, several patents describe the removal of gaseous pollutants using advanced oxidation technologies. For example, CN119258735A [20] combines microwave-assisted photocatalysis with two-stage ammonia absorption for simultaneous SO₂, NO_x, and Hg removal from flue gas. Similarly, WO2014158344A2 [21] integrates UV-driven oxidation and chemical absorption for multi-pollutant treatment. Another example, US9937466B2 [22], focuses on the degradation of amines and nitrosamines in wastewater from carbon capture systems using UV/H₂O₂ and ozone. Although these systems demonstrate the potential of AOPs, they are designed for specific pollutant mixtures and often involve complex setups with multiple reagents or catalysts.

In contrast, our study presents a simplified two-stage UV/H₂O₂ system targeting gaseous ammonia, with the added benefit of partial nitrogen recovery. The absence of metal catalysts and the straightforward configuration make the approach energy-efficient and scalable for industrial applications, in line with circular economy principles.

Another advantage of this approach is the use of the first stage (photolytic reactor) to eliminate the accompanying organic pollutants that may be present in the effluent alongside ammonia. The proposed technology not only enhances ammonia degradation but also facilitates the recovery of valuable nitrogen compounds from wastewater, aligning with the circular economy.

The objectives of this study can be summarized as: (1) evaluate the efficiency of two-stage technology utilizing advanced oxidation processes in reducing ammonia emissions from waste air; (2) determine optimal conditions for ammonia conversion absorbed into water; (3) study possible recovery of formed nitrogen compounds (NO₂/NO₃).

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Chemicals

Chemicals used in the experiments were purchased from chemical companies with the following purities: ammonium hydroxide (25 %, p.

a., Mach Chemikálie Ltd., Czech Republic), hydrogen peroxide (30 %, p. a., Mach Chemikálie Ltd. Czech Republic) and potassium hydroxide (p. a., Mach Chemikálie Ltd. Czech Republic).

2.2. Analytical method

Ammonia concentrations in the air were monitored using an FTIR analyzer (Antaris IGS Analyzer, Nicolet CZ Ltd., Czech Republic). Airflow speed and relative humidity were measured using a multimeter (testo 440, Testo SE & Co. KGaA, Germany) equipped with airflow speed and relative humidity probes. Ammonia concentrations in the hydrogen peroxide solution were determined using the Nessler method and analyzed with a photometer (PF-12^{Plus}, Macherey-Nagel GmbH & Co. KG, Germany). Total nitrogen (TN) values were measured using TOC analyzer (FormacsHT-I, Skalar Ltd., Breda, The Netherlands) with an ND25 detector. The pH of the hydrogen peroxide solution was measured using a pH meter (Multi 3420, WTW Measuring and Analytical Technology Ltd., Czech Republic) equipped with a pH probe (SenTix 940–3, Xylem Inc., USA). Nitrite and nitrate concentrations in the hydrogen peroxide solution were determined using an ion chromatograph (Eco IC, Metrohm, Czech Republic).

2.3. Experimental apparatus

Experiments with ammonia-polluted air were conducted using a two-stage experimental setup (Fig. 1).

To introduce ammonia into the system, air was bubbled through a 1 % ammonium hydroxide solution in an enrichment reactor, which was maintained at 30 °C in a heated water bath (Stuart SW15D, Cole-Parmer LLC, USA). The ammonia-enriched gas was then mixed with air in the inlet pipe leading to the photolytic reactor (R1). This stainless-steel reactor had an internal volume of $28 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$ and contained four horizontally placed low-pressure mercury UV lamps ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 185/254 \text{ nm}$, 80 W, UVC-80 W T5 4P/O3, UVC Servis Ltd., Czech Republic), arranged parallel to the flow direction (Fig. 2).

In the second stage, the air flowed into a wet counter-current scrubber (R2) (Fig. 3). A hydrogen peroxide solution (0.1 mol · dm⁻³) was circulated in the scrubber between a tank ($158 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$) at the

Fig. 1. Schematic drawing of the technology.

Fig. 2. 3D model of the photolytic reactor (R1) with dimensions.

Fig. 3. 3D model of the chemical scrubber (R2) with dimensions.

bottom and two spray nozzles (full-cone type – spray angle 60° – from Hennlich) at the top. The total volume of the wet counter-current scrubber is $552 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$ while the dripped volume was $328 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$.

The scrubber does not contain any packing. The liquid solution circulates in a semi-closed loop, with continuous recirculation between the bottom tank and the top spray section. The liquid flow rate is $800 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. The entire experimental setup, including the wet scrubber and reactors, was designed and assembled in cooperation with Dekonta Inc., ensuring consistency with industrial design practices.

A stainless-steel tubular reactor (R3) ($33 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ m}^3$) connected to the scrubber tank facilitated the generation of hydroxyl radicals (HO^\bullet) due to the presence of three UV lamps ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 254 \text{ nm}$, 200 W, Philips, Netherlands) placed in quartz tubes with a diameter of 40 mm and a glass thickness of 2 mm (Fig. 4).

2.4. Experimental setup

Experiments were carried with three air flows (28 ; 57 and $113 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$) and 2 inlet ammonia concentrations (25 and 50 ppmv).

The normal experimental run was as follows:

1. filling the wet scrubber (R2) with clean water and taking a water sample,

Fig. 4. 3D model of the tubular reactor (R3) reactor with dimensions.

2. introducing ammonia to the system using the enrichment reactor,
3. adjusting the input ammonia concentration and waiting for stabilization,
4. turning on the lamps in R1,
5. the lamps run in R1 for 45 min,
6. turning on water circulation in R2 + pouring in hydrogen peroxide (2 L) + turning on the lamps in R3,
7. the lamps run in both R1 and R3 for 60 min,
8. taking a water sample before and after the tubular reactor (sample points R3_1 and R3_2) + turning off all lamps and water circulation in R2,
9. shutting off the ammonia.

During each experiment, a sample of tap water was taken from a filled scrubber and a control sample of tap water from scrubber after the photolytic process and before turning on the spray nozzles.

Conversion of ammonia was chosen as an indicating factor of ammonia degradation (Eqs. (1), (2)).

$$X = \frac{n_0 - n}{n_0} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

$$X = \frac{c_0 - c}{c_0} \cdot 100; V = \text{const.} \quad (2)$$

X is a degree of conversion of ammonia (%), n_0 is the inlet substance amount of ammonia (mol), n is the substance amount of ammonia at the set time (mol), c_0 is the inlet concentration of ammonia (ppmv) and c is the concentration of ammonia at the set time (ppmv).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Experiments without pH adjustment

3.1.1. Degradation of NH_3 from gas phase

In the first stage of the technology, photolytic reactions occur in the gas phase. Intense UV radiation ($\lambda = 185$ nm) generates excited singlet oxygen atoms $O(^1D)$ according to equations (Eq. (3)), which react with molecular oxygen to form ozone (Eq. (4)). Ozone absorbs a photon with wavelength of 254 nm, decomposing into molecular oxygen and an excited oxygen atom in the singlet D (Eq. (5) [23,24]). Intense UV radiation can also form hydroxyl radicals from air humidity (Eq. (6) [23], or directly reacts with ammonia molecules (Eq (7) [24,25]). The products of these photolytic reactions (Eqs. (5), (6)) and other radical reaction (Eq. (8) [23] further react with ammonia according to the following equations (Eqs. (9), (10)) [26,27].

It is clear oxidation of gaseous ammonia with UV irradiation is a complex process employing number of radical reactions. The primary oxidation pathway of ammonia is represented by reaction (Eq. (10)), although it is not the fastest [24]. The oxidation of ammonia molecule by singlet oxygen (Eq. (9)) has faster rate constant [28], however, the generation of hydroxyl radicals ($OH \cdot$) comes from multiple sources (Eqs. (6) and (8)) making the oxidation of ammonia more probable and in addition, the formation of singlet oxygen requires three reaction steps (Eqs. (3)–(5)) even more lowering the probability of ammonia oxidation (Eq. (9)). Formed amino radicals (NH_2) subsequently react with oxygen (O_2), hydroxyl radicals ($OH \cdot$) and ozone (O_3) which is critical for oxidation into nitrosyl and nitrate compounds (Eqs. (11)–(15) [17,25,26,29]).

The oxidation follows multi step radical mechanism where each intermediate can be further oxidized by each oxidation species. The most obvious are oxygen, hydroxyl radicals and ozone, however, there are also singlet and triplet oxygen present in the mixture [28]. However, as mentioned above the oxidation of ammonia proceeds primarily by hydroxyl radicals.

The presence of emerging NO_x species downstream of the photolytic reactor was monitored using FT-IR spectroscopy. The total concentration of these compounds did not exceed 2.5 ppmv in any experiment. These results indicate that the dominant pathway for ammonia degradation ultimately leads to its decomposition into nitrogen and water (Eq.

(16) [24].

The conversion of ammonia was strongly dependent on the air flow rate, with a maximum conversion of 24 % achieved at an air flow rate of $28 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and an input ammonia concentration of 25 ppmv (Fig. 5). These are excellent findings, especially when compared to other study dealing with mitigation of ammonia from animal housing. Even though, they used photocatalysis and very long treatment times (up to 170 s) they reached ammonia reduction between 5 to 9 % [30]. In their study, the initial ammonia concentration was 23 ± 3 ppmv, which is comparable to our experimental conditions. The treatment time in our case is 3.6 s for the air flow $28 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$.

3.1.2. Degradation of NH_3 from water

The second stage of the technology involves the absorption of ammonia into water (R2), followed by its photochemical degradation in a tubular reactor (R3). Under the specified conditions, the scrubber demonstrated high efficiency, achieving an ammonia removal rate of 98 % from the air flow (Fig. 6). Analysis of the measured data indicates that the air flow rate and inlet ammonia concentration had a negligible impact on the absorption process. The variations in ammonia absorption across different flow rates and input concentrations were within the experimental margin of error. This can be explained by the fact that the hydrogen peroxide solution in the scrubber was far from saturation under the tested conditions, maintaining a strong capacity for ammonia absorption even at higher flow rates and concentrations.

As mentioned, a tubular reactor was introduced into the system to generate hydroxyl radicals ($HO \cdot$) primarily from hydrogen peroxide with the goal to oxidize dissolved ammonia (NH_3) to nitrite (NO_2^-) and subsequently nitrate (NO_3^-), as described by overall reactions (17)–(19) [17].

However, this conversion did not occur during the initial experiments. The pH remained stable around 7.5 during the experiments regardless of air flow or input ammonia concentrations (Fig. S1). Ion chromatography confirmed that there was no increase in nitrite or nitrate concentrations (data not shown). Instead, ammonia remained in its ammonium form. This is also confirmed by the increasing value of total

Fig. 5. Photolytic degradation of ammonia in R1 in dependence on the air flow at the different inlet ammonia concentration.

Fig. 6. Dependence of the average ammonia removal on the air flow at the different inlet ammonia concentration in R2.

nitrogen concentration in the hydrogen peroxide solution at higher inlet ammonia concentrations and higher flow rates (Fig. S2).

Following the initial experiments, a series of tests were performed to investigate the effect of various processes on the photodegradation of ammonia in solution. The hydrogen peroxide-ammonia solution circulated only between R2 and R3, where three different conditions were set: (1) blank = ammonia evaporation/ammonia sorption in the system; (2) photolysis = photolysis of ammonia in an aqueous environment; and (3) photo-oxidation = data from a normal experiment without adjusting the conditions for comparison with other conditions. Surprisingly, none of the above conditions had a significant impact on the degradation of ammonia (Fig. S3).

Seeking to improve the photo-degradation of ammonia in hydrogen peroxide solution, a study by Wang et al. [17] reported that higher pH (>9.2) is more favorable for nitrite and nitrate production. At lower pH, the reaction is less efficient because the dominant species is NH_4^+ rather than NH_3 . In an aqueous solution, ammonia exists as NH_4OH , a molecule that does not undergo decomposition at a wavelength of 254 nm. However, at pH values greater than 10.8 production of nitrates and nitrites decreases again. This is due to the hydrogen peroxide dissociates into the compound HO_2^- (Eq. (20)) which reacts preferentially with HO^\bullet (Eq. (21)). The product (HO_2^\bullet) of mentioned reaction has also higher kinetic rate constant (Eq. (22)) which is reducing the availability of HO^\bullet for ammonia oxidation (Eq. (23)) [17,31].

Furthermore, the concentration of H_2O_2 has a significant effect on the reaction: too low concentration of H_2O_2 is insufficient for efficient oxidation of NH_3 , while too high concentration leads to blocking of the HO^\bullet by unreacted hydrogen peroxide, thus preventing the oxidation of ammonia (Eqs. (24), (25)).

3.2. Experiments with pH adjustment

In this set of experiments the dosage of H_2O_2 was lowered (from $0.1 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$ to $0.0026 \text{ mol} \cdot \text{dm}^{-3}$) and KOH was added to achieve the required pH value throughout the experiment. The benefit of adding

KOH is the potential formation of KNO_3 which can be further used as fertilizer.

In the first stage of the technology, ammonia is degraded in the gas phase through photolytic processes. Based on the reaction mechanisms and actual experimental measurements, neither pH adjustment nor modifications such as varying the hydrogen peroxide concentration have any significantly influence on the ammonia degradation efficiency in this phase. These parameters primarily affect the aqueous-phase oxidation in the second stage. Therefore, further data evaluation focused exclusively on the photo-oxidation of ammonia in the hydrogen peroxide solution.

pH adjustments significantly increased the potential for ammonia oxidation as reflected in the results obtained from ion chromatography (Fig. 7). Each individual sample was analyzed by total nitrogen (TN), ion chromatography (NO_3^- and NO_2^-), and Nessler method (NH_4^+). The ion chromatography and Nessler method data were then converted to nitrogen concentration (labeled like N/NO_2^- , N/NO_3^- and N/NH_4^+) to allow comparison with total nitrogen.

3.2.1. Degradation of NH_3 in batch arrangement

First, ammonia was applied to the system directly into the tank in the scrubber and the stabilization of the formation of nitrates and nitrites was monitored at the pH 10. Batch arrangement was used in order to follow total nitrogen (TN) concentration over time (Fig. 7).

The initial ammonia concentration was $9.9 \text{ mg} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$, which corresponds to 7.7 mg of nitrogen per liter ($\text{N} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) when expressed as nitrogen. A total of 155 mL of H_2O_2 (added in three doses: 55 mL , 50 mL , and 50 mL) during the experiment and 37.1 g of KOH in five doses were introduced into the system to maintain a stable pH value. The reaction equilibrium was established after 4 h of measurement. In this moment the system contained the substances in those concentrations (Table 1):

The Ammonia loss corresponds to 46 % conversion. The same results were achieved by control measurements after 5 h.

3.2.2. Degradation of NH_3 in continuous flow arrangement

The next experiment was conducted in the usual experimental setup (continuous flow arrangement) at a flow rate of $113 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{h}^{-1}$ and an air ammonia concentration of 50 ppmv (Fig. 8). Sample zero represents ammonia-enriched tap water, originating from the scrubbing of contaminated air prior to the onset of photochemical degradation. The absorption of ammonia into water persisted throughout the entire experiment which was confirmed by increasing TN over time.

In this case the highest amount of nitrogen calculated from NO_2^- ($\text{C}_\text{N} = 2.6 \text{ mg}$ of $\text{N} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$) was recorded after three hours (Table 2). The maximum nitrogen concentration from NO_3^- was $\text{C}_\text{N} = 3.4 \text{ mg}$ of $\text{N} \cdot \text{L}^{-1}$. This value is the same as in the previous measurement (Fig. 7), however, the sum of nitrogen concentration originating from NO_2^- and NO_3^- ($\text{C}_\text{N} =$

Fig. 7. Ammonia oxidation and $\text{NO}_2^-/\text{NO}_3^-$ formation at pH 10.0 in batch arrangement.

Table 1

Concentration of substances and calculated concentration of Nitrogen in batch arrangement.

	Units	NH ₄ ⁺ (initial)	NH ₄ ⁺ (after 4 h)	NO ₂ ⁻ (after 4 h)	NO ₃ ⁻ (after 4 h)
Concentration of substances	mg · L ⁻¹	9.9	5.3	3.9	17.3
Calculated concentration of Nitrogen	mg of N · L ⁻¹	7.7	4.1	1.2	3.9

Fig. 8. Ammonia oxidation and NO₂⁻/NO₃⁻ formation at pH 10.0 in continuous flow arrangement.**Table 2**

Concentration of substances and calculated concentration of Nitrogen in continuous flow arrangement.

	Units	NH ₄ ⁺ (initial)	NH ₄ ⁺ (after 3 h)	NO ₂ ⁻ (after 3 h)	NO ₃ ⁻ (after 3 h)
Concentration of substances	mg · L ⁻¹	10.4	16.5	8.5	15.1
Calculated concentration of Nitrogen	mg of N · L ⁻¹	8.1	12.8	2.6	3.4

6 mg of N · L⁻¹ is 1.7 mg of N · L⁻¹ higher than in the Fig. 7 (experiments after 3 h were compared), when the sum of nitrogen concentration from nitrite and nitrate was 4.3 mg of N · L⁻¹. This is likely due to the continuous increase in ammonia concentration in the solution because of the ongoing process. Maximizing nitrate and nitrite production in this technology will be the subject of further studies.

A key limitation of our study is the relatively short duration of experiments and not sufficient conversion rate of ammonia to nitrites/nitrates. Long-term stability tests would be beneficial to assess the technology's performance over extended periods, which is critical for industrial applications.

3.3. Figures-of-merit

The assessment of various technologies for ammonia removal from wastewater and air is challenging, especially when different principles and reactor designs are involved. A reliable comparison of these technologies requires quantifiable performance indicators, particularly those related to operational efficiency and cost. One of the key metrics used for this purpose is the energy consumption associated with pollutant removal. A commonly employed parameter is the Electrical Energy per Order (E_{EO}), which represents the amount of energy required

to reduce the ammonia concentration by one order of magnitude (Eq. (26)). For low initial concentrations of ammonia, the E_{EO} can be expressed as follows [31]:

$$E_{EO} = \frac{P}{F \cdot \log \frac{c_{in}}{c_{out}}} \quad (26)$$

where E_{EO} is the electric demand for the degradation of pollutants (kWh · m⁻³ · order⁻¹), P is the rated power (kW), F is the air flow through the unit (m³ · h⁻¹), c_{in} is the inlet ammonia concentration (ppmv) and c_{out} is the outlet ammonia concentration (ppmv).

As noted by Crittenden et al. [31], this simplified form of the E_{EO} equation is valid under the assumption of pseudo-first-order kinetics, which typically applies to pollutant concentrations is low enough that the optical absorption and reaction kinetics remain linear. It is also recommended by IUPAC as published by Bolton et al. (2001) [32], where the EEO is used as a standardized figure-of-merit for comparing AOP systems based on energy efficiency. The linear reaction kinetic was fulfilled in our conditions and used concentrations, which is showing in our previous publication [24].

Table S1 presents the calculated cost of treating 1 m³ of polluted air, as well as the cost of 1 h of treatment for an inlet ammonia concentration of 50 ppmv and an air flow rate of 113 m³ · h⁻¹. The calculations include the average electricity cost per kWh (0.12 €, 2024, Czech Republic), the average cost of tap water per m³ (4.48 €, 2024, Czech Republic), and the cost of the required chemicals. The results indicate that a lower dosage of hydrogen peroxide combined with the addition of potassium hydroxide reduces the hourly treatment cost by a factor of 2.6, from 3.268 € · h⁻¹ to 1.238 € · h⁻¹.

The cost evaluations of UV/H₂O₂ and other AOP systems, such as those reported by Michael-Kordatou et al. (2018) [33], demonstrate that EEO values and associated treatment costs vary significantly depending on target compounds and operational settings. For example, the reported treatment cost for micropollutants using UV-based AOPs ranges from 0.5 to 3.5 € · m⁻³, depending on the specific configuration and energy consumption. By comparison, the operational cost of our system (1.24 and 3.27 € · h⁻¹ for a flow rate of 113 m³ · h⁻¹ and 50 ppmv NH₃) translates to 0.011 and 0.029 € · m⁻³, which places our technology in a cost-effective range relative to other UV-based AOPs. Moreover, the added benefit of partial nitrogen recovery further enhances the economic and environmental viability of the proposed system.

4. Conclusions

This research has successfully developed a two-stage system for efficient ammonia removal from air using photochemical processes. Our experiments have shown that the use of hydrogen peroxide as a hydroxyl radical source in combination with a photolytic reactor can achieve a significant reduction in airborne ammonia concentration (98 % conversion). The maximum ammonia conversion in aqueous media was achieved under specific conditions, suggesting that maintaining the pH within the optimal range of 9.2–10.8 and applying gradual dosing of H₂O₂ and KOH play a key role in the efficiency of the process.

We further identified that our technology not only meets the requirements for ammonia emission reduction, but also contributes to the circular economy by producing nitrate (15.1 mg · L⁻¹) and nitrite (8.5 mg · L⁻¹), which can be used as raw materials for fertilizer production. In this way, our solution becomes environmentally sustainable and economically viable.

Based on the results of our experiments, it is clear that the implementation of this technology in industrial plants can contribute to a significant improvement of air quality and protection of public health. Due to the increasing pressure to comply with emission limits within the European Union, our technology is expected to find wide application in power plants and other industrial sectors.

In conclusion, the innovative approach to removing ammonia from

contaminated air represents a significant step towards a greener future and environmental protection. We further recommend continued research aimed at optimizing the processes and expanding the applications of this technology in various industries.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Tomáš Prostějovský: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Lucie Spáčilová:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Investigation. **Martin Reli:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Project administration, Conceptualization. **Radim Žebrák:** Writing – original draft, Methodology. **Kamila Kočí:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Supervision, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seppur.2025.134017>.

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